

1 **Summer assessment of subjective heat strain and mental health among outdoor**
2 **workers: investigating signs of heat adaptation with ecological momentary assessments**

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11 **Background:** Outdoor workers are particularly vulnerable to high summer temperatures, yet
12 little is known about whether their susceptibility decreases over the course of the season, a
13 phenomenon referred to as intra-seasonal adaptation. **Methods:** We conducted an intensive,
14 3-month longitudinal monitoring study of 13 outdoor workers during June-August 2023 in
15 Catalonia (northeastern Spain, N=822 observations). Participants provided daily ecological
16 momentary assessments for daily subjective heat strain (DSHS), fatigue, cognitive state,
17 stress, anger, and negative mood. Linear mixed effects models assessed associations between
18 temperature and health outcomes across the entire summer period, with additional covariate
19 adjustment for month and a temperature–month interaction term to explore intra-seasonal
20 adaptation. **Results:** All psychological indicators worsened at higher temperatures. DSHS,
21 anger, and negative mood were lower in July and August compared with June, suggesting
22 some degree of intra-seasonal adaptation. Averaged estimates showed higher DSHS in June
23 than July and August up to 25-26 °C, and higher negative mood in June than July up to 23°C.
24 Increases in relative humidity were associated with worsened DSHS and stress. **Conclusions:**
25 Our findings support heat as a consistent stressor across different health outcomes, while
26 providing evidence regarding intra-seasonal adaptation among outdoor workers across the
27 summer for subjective heat strain and mood. Results highlight the relevance of considering
28 temporal dynamics in observational heat-health research and for interventions protecting
29 workers in a warming climate.

30 **1. Introduction**

31 Outdoor workers, particularly those in sectors with peak summer activity and high physical
32 demands are highly vulnerable to heat, a risk that is exacerbated by climate change and rising
33 global temperatures^{1,2}. Many jobs restrict heat-protection measures (like pacing, hydration,
34 or ventilation), and fixed rhythms or performance-based pay further limit rest, increasing
35 heat-related health risks³. Today, it is estimated that more than one in three workers globally
36 exposed to heat suffers from heat strain². Occupational heat strain refers to the physiological
37 effect of environmental heat stress on the body which can lead to impaired physiological
38 functions⁴, mental health issues⁵, reduced cognitive state⁶, fatigue^{7,8} and poor sleep^{9,10}.
39 Known pathways for these associations includes heat exposure activating the neuroendocrine
40 system managing stress responses triggering cortisol production, while also severely
41 disrupting sleep quality, both of which impair concentration and increase fatigue and
42 irritability, prompting or worsening existing mental-health disorders^{11,12}. Ultimately, these
43 effects can also increase the risk of work injuries^{13,14} and lead to severe heat illness that can
44 eventually cause death^{15,16}.

45 Beyond estimating the negative impacts of heat on various health outcomes, recent research
46 has begun to investigate whether, and in what ways humans may be able to adapt to heat¹⁷.
47 By adaptation (or acclimatisation), we here refer to the reduction in the vulnerability to heat
48 regarding specific health-related outcomes^{18,19}. Some evidence indicates that the cumulative
49 exposure to heat may promote acclimatisation at the physiological level. A meta-analysis²⁰
50 showed better physiological responses to experimental tests, such as improved sweating, skin
51 blood flow, and lowered body temperatures, by the end of summer compared to its beginning,
52 suggesting that acclimatisation can occur with continued exposure throughout the hot season.

53 While physiological adaptation to heat may suggest the possibility of parallel psychological
54 adaptation, this hypothesis remains largely underexplored, despite growing recognition that
55 psychological functioning and mental health are central concerns in occupational heat
56 exposure⁵. An ecological momentary assessment (EMA) study conducted in Chicago²¹ found
57 that adults from the general population reported greater thermal comfort and lower thermal
58 perception in outdoor environments later in the summer compared to the beginning under

59 comparable temperatures, although no similar improvements were observed for mood-related
60 outcomes. Importantly, this study relied on repeated cross-sectional design with independent
61 samples of individuals at each time point in the seven two-week waves, preventing any
62 inference about within-individual psychological intra-seasonal adaptation.

63 Building on existing literature on physiological adaptation, the present study aims to detect
64 signs of heat adaptation in outdoor workers, at the within-individual level and focusing on
65 psychological outcomes. Over a three-month summer period, participants completed brief
66 smartphone EMAs at the end of each workday, reporting how much they suffered from heat
67 during the day (referred here as daily subjective heat strain, DSHS) alongside self-reported
68 items assessing several mental health-related outcomes: fatigue, cognitive state and mood.
69 Using this longitudinal dataset, we assessed whether within-individual associations between
70 heat exposure and psychological outcomes existed and whether they changed over the course
71 of the summer. We expected to observe patterns of diminished associations between
72 temperature and the psychological outcomes across the summer, consistent with heat
73 adaptation. We also hypothesised that temperature would show the strongest relationship
74 with DSHS compared with mental health outcomes²¹, since the latter may be influenced by
75 additional non-thermal factors, thus leading to smaller associations with heat.

76 **2. Methods**

77 **2.1. Study Design and Participants**

78 The present study follows an observational, intensive longitudinal design with a daily EMA
79 of DSHS and mental health outcomes over a period of 3 months. Data were collected between
80 June 1st and August 31st 2023 in Catalonia, north-eastern Spain, among 13 outdoor
81 agricultural and solar panel workers. Missing data because of holidays and non-response
82 were excluded from the analyses. The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the
83 Ethics Committee for Research with Medicines of Parc de Salut MAR (project number
84 2021/9857/I, June 1st 2021), in compliance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of
85 Helsinki. All participants provided informed consent prior to participation.

86 Before the study started, participants answered a baseline questionnaire regarding their
87 workhours, substance use, ethnicity, physical wellbeing (BMI, activity level, diet, chronic

illnesses, and medications), work experience and use of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE). All items from the baseline questionnaire, as well as descriptive statistics of the sample are provided in Supplementary 1 tables S1 and S2.

2.2. **Psychological outcomes**

At the end of each workday, participants completed a brief set of EMA questions (in Spanish or Catalan depending on their preference) via a smartphone application (m-path²²) assessing DSHS, fatigue, cognitive state, and mood (see Table 1). The DSHS item was adapted from the Environmental Symptoms Questionnaire²³ (ESQ). DSHS severity was rated on a 11-point scale (see table 1) and is consistent with single-item formats previously used in EMA research²⁴ and in subjective heat stress research²⁵. Items assessing fatigue, cognitive state and mood were adapted from previous EMA studies^{26,27}. Mental health scores were measured to align with the DSHS item in the app, such that higher scores indicate worse mental health.

Table 1. Items from daily, after-work EMA survey

Dimension	Sub-dimension	Item	Attributes
DSHS		How much did you suffer from the heat while working today?	0 (not at all, heat wasn't an issue) to 10 (a lot, heat was impossible to manage)
Fatigue		What is your level of fatigue now?	0 (I feel very awake and full of energy) to 10 (I feel very tired, without energy)
Mood	Anger	How would you say you felt today?	0 (Absolutely cheerful and good humored) to 10 (Absolutely irritable and angry)
	Negative mood	How would you say you felt today?	0 (Absolutely content and happy) to 10 (Absolutely sad and depressed)
	Stress	How would you say you felt today?	0 (Absolutely calm and relaxed) to 10 (Absolutely stressed, nervous and tense)
Cognitive state		How easy is to focus your mind right now?	0 (My mind feels sharp and quick to focus) to 10 (Concentrating feels very difficult or slow)

2.3. **Temperature**

Daily outdoor average, maximum and minimum temperature at each exact work location were estimated by bilinearly interpolating a high-resolution, 300-m gridded dataset provided

104 by the Catalan Meteorological Agency (Meteocat)^{28,29}. Unlike assigning exposure based on
105 distant weather stations (potentially several tens of kilometres away), gridded data provides
106 high spatial accuracy, significantly reducing exposure misclassification and better capturing
107 local microclimates³⁰.

108 2.4. Control variables

109 Analogously, daily outdoor average relative humidity (RH) at each exact work location were
110 estimated from a similar gridded meteorological dataset obtained from Meteocat^{28,29}.
111 Participants were also asked to wear an activity monitor continuously on their non-dominant
112 wrist throughout the study period, the *Withings Steel HR* smartwatch, a commercial-grade
113 activity monitor, using a triaxial accelerometer for activity measures, in order to obtain daily
114 step counts as an indicator of the workload for each working day³¹⁻³⁴.

115 2.5. Statistical Analyses

116 We used 3 sets of linear mixed-effects models to estimate the overall pattern of association
117 between temperature and the psychological outcomes, with each outcome (DSHS, fatigue,
118 cognitive state, anger, stress, and negative mood) as independent variables, and the daily
119 mean outdoor temperature as dependent variables. A set of covariates were a priori selected
120 based on evidence from previous studies⁴ (see Figure S1 in Supplementary material 1 for bi-
121 variate associations), and then the final model included covariates based on models' fit and
122 parsimony using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criterion
123 (BIC). The first set of linear mixed models (*whole summer models*) include the following
124 terms for each participant i on day t : the psychological outcome (Y_{it}), the measurement of the
125 dependent variable in the previous day ($Y_{i,t-1}$) to account for autocorrelation, relative
126 humidity (RH_{it}), age (Age_i), sex (Sex_i) and the daily number of steps ($Steps_{it}$). We fitted
127 the models including random intercepts (u_i) for each participant, accounting for different
128 baseline levels of the outcome in each participant.

$$129 \quad Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Temp_{it} + \beta_2 RH_{it} + \beta_3 Y_{i,t-1} + \beta_4 Steps_{it} + \beta_5 Age_i + \beta_6 Sex_i + u_i$$
$$130 \quad \quad \quad + \varepsilon_{it}$$

131 The second set of models aimed to assess the role of time in the association between
132 temperature and psychological outcomes (*model including months*), including a categorical
133 variable for summer month (June, July, August), to test whether psychological outcomes
134 varied from one month to another.

$$135 \quad Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Temp_t + \beta_2 July_t + \beta_3 Aug_t + \beta_4 RH_t + \beta_5 Y_{i,t-1} + \beta_6 Steps_{it}$$
$$136 \quad + \beta_7 Age_i + \beta_8 Sex_i + u_i + \varepsilon_{it}$$

137 At last, the third set of regressions (*temperature-by-month interaction models*) added an
138 interaction term between daily outdoor average temperature and each month to specifically
139 test time-varying associations with temperature.

$$140 \quad Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Temp_t + \beta_2 July_t + \beta_3 Aug_t$$
$$141 \quad + \beta_4 (Temp_t \times July_t) + \beta_5 (Temp_t \times Aug_t) + \beta_6 RH_t + \beta_7 Y_{i,t-1}$$
$$142 \quad + \beta_8 Steps_{it} + \beta_9 Age_i + \beta_{10} Sex_i + u_i + \varepsilon_{it}$$

143 We treated daily mean temperature as a same-day exposure, since preliminary analyses using
144 moving averages consistently yielded smaller effect sizes and no significant improvements
145 in models' performance, while models including temperature lags presented unlikely
146 negative slopes and moderate multicollinearity according to the variance inflation factor
147 (VIF, see supplementary material 2).

148 We complemented the third sets of regressions with a set of marginal means (MM) analyses.
149 MMs were used to compare the predicted values of the outcome at specific representative
150 temperatures across months, holding other variables constant. Specifically, continuous
151 covariates were held at their sample mean, and categorical covariates were held at their
152 reference category. This method provides an interpretable way to test how predicted health
153 outcomes differ between months at specific temperature levels, as well as to identify
154 temperature thresholds where the differences between months emerge. For the models with
155 the interaction, we restricted the analyses to values (19-27°C) observed in all months for
156 outdoor temperatures.

157 We also tested potential non-linear associations between daily temperature and health
158 outcomes by adding either a quadratic term of temperature or a 3-degree spline of
159 temperature to the baseline models. Model comparisons showed no improvement in model
160 fit, indicating that the associations were approximately linear within the observed
161 temperature range (see tables S2, S4, S6, S8, S10 of supplementary material 2).

162 All analyses were performed using RStudio using the packages lme4 and emmeans. The data
163 and code used in the present study can be found on OSF (<https://osf.io/jxq43/>).

164 **3. Results**

165 **3.1. Descriptive statistics**

166 The study included 13 participants, most of whom were men (77%, n=10). Ten of the
167 participants worked in agriculture (77%), while the other three worked as solar panel
168 installers. About one-third (37%) were self-employed, and the remainder were employed
169 workers. Participants ranged in age from 27 to 45 years (Mean, M = 34, Standard Deviation,
170 SD = 5.2), and nearly 70% had completed tertiary education.

171 Across the summer, participants completed 822 post-work EMA surveys, with an average of
172 56 responses per person (average response rate of 88%). During the study period, mean
173 ambient temperature (across 24 hours) was 24.2 °C (SD = 3.2), accompanied by an average
174 relative humidity of 68% (SD = 10). Table S3 of the supplementary material 1 displays
175 descriptive statistics of the study outcomes and exposure variables.

176 **3.2. Associations between temperature and psychological outcomes across the** 177 **summer (*whole summer models*)**

178 We observed positive associations between outdoor temperature and all psychological
179 outcomes (see Figure 1), so that higher temperatures were consistently linked with poorer
180 psychological outcomes after controlling for RH, lag 1 outcome, step counts age and sex (see
181 table S3, column 1, and table S7 of supplementary material 1). For each 1 °C change in
182 temperature, the estimated coefficients were 0.43 points for DSHS (95% CI: 0.38–0.48), 0.17
183 for fatigue (95% CI: 0.12–0.21), and 0.16 for cognitive state (95% CI: 0.12–0.20). For the

184 mood-related outcomes, the corresponding coefficients were 0.11 for negative mood (95%
185 CI: 0.08–0.15), 0.12 for stress (95% CI: 0.08–0.16), and 0.14 for anger (95% CI: 0.10–0.18).

186 Figure 1. Associations between outdoor temperature and psychological outcomes.

187
188 **Note.** Point estimates and 95% confidence intervals from linear mixed-effects models reflect the average effect
189 of daily average outdoor temperature (per 1°C increase) on each outcome, adjusting for relative humidity, step
190 count, age, sex, and the previous day’s score. Positive values indicate worsening symptoms with higher
191 temperatures.

192 3.3. Associations between temperature and psychological outcomes across 193 specific months (*model including months*)

194 Figure 2 presents the estimated month-to-month differences in psychological outcomes. Full
195 model outputs are provided in supplementary material 1 (table S4, column 2, and table S8).
196 DSHS scores for July (–0.54, CI: –0.85 to –0.22) and August (–0.56, CI: –0.88 to –0.23)
197 were significantly lower than June. Anger in July (–0.27, CI: –0.53 to –0.01) and August (–
198 0.27, CI: –0.55 to –0.00) also differed significantly from June, like negative mood in July (–
199 0.25, CI: –0.50 to –0.00) and August (–0.28, CI: –0.54 to 0.02) compared to June. Fatigue
200 and cognitive state did not exhibit statistically significant differences across the summer
201 months.

202 Figure 2. Changes in psychological outcomes across the summer months.

203

204 **Note.** Estimated month effects (reference = June) from linear mixed-effects models are shown for each
205 outcome, adjusted for daily average temperature, relative humidity, step counts, age, sex, and the previous day's
206 score. Points represent the estimated difference in outcomes for July and August compared with June; error bars
207 indicate 95% confidence intervals. Negative estimates reflect lower symptom severity.

208 **3.4. Associations between temperature and psychological outcomes including the**
209 **interaction between month and temperature (*temperature-by-month***
210 ***interaction models*)**

211 In a third set of models, we included temperature-by-month interaction terms. Full model
212 outputs are provided in supplementary material 1 (table S4, column 3 and table S9). The
213 interaction between month and temperature was statistically significant for DSHS (month of
214 July in comparison to the month of June). Model-based contrasts indicated that DSHS values
215 in July and August differed from those from June within specific temperature ranges:
216 approximately 19–25 °C for contrasts between June and July, and 21–26 °C for contrasts
217 between June and August. Outside these ranges, confidence intervals included zero,
218 indicating no statistically significant differences (Figure 3).

219 A statistically significant month-by-temperature interaction was also observed for negative
220 mood. Model-based contrasts indicated differences between July and June within the

221 approximate range of 19–23 °C; confidence intervals included zero outside this range,
222 indicating no statistically significant differences between months beyond this interval.

223 Figure 3. Marginal means contrasts of daily subjective heat strain (DSHS, panel A) and
224 negative mood (panel B) at fixed covariates, by month.

225 **Note.** Figure depicts the contrasts in predicted daily subjective heat strain (DSHS) between June and July (red)
226 and between June and August (blue) across the average outdoor temperature range observed in all summer
227 months. Shaded areas represent 95% confidence intervals. Positive values indicate higher DSHS in June
228 compared to the reference month. Contrasts were derived from mixed-effects models including an interaction
229 term between temperature (continuous) and month, assuming linear associations within each month. The
230 differences were most evident at moderate temperatures (around 21-25 °C), while at lower and higher
231 temperatures the confidence intervals overlapped zero.

232 3.5. Role of covariates

233 RH was significantly associated with DSHS (0.17,95% CI: 0.03 – 0.32, see Table S3,
234 supplementary material 1) and stress (0.13, CI: 0.01 – 0.25, see Table S7, supplementary
235 material 1). RH was not significantly associated with cognitive state, fatigue, anger or
236 negative mood. Step counts was significantly associated with DSHS (0.12, 95% CI: 0.08 –
237 0.16, see table 3. Appendix, column 1). We did not find significant associations between step
238 counts and other outcomes. Neither sex nor age were significantly associated with the
239 psychological outcomes.

240 4. Discussion

241 To our knowledge, this is the first within-individual longitudinal study examining signs of
242 seasonal adaptation in psychological outcomes among outdoor workers exposed to heat.
243 Overall, higher temperatures were consistently associated with poorer psychological
244 outcomes, including subjective heat strain and mental health indicators, supporting existing
245 evidence linking heat exposure to psychological distress^{35,36}. However, we observed seasonal
246 improvements in subjective heat vulnerability, with lower subjective heat strain, anger, and
247 negative mood in July and August compared with June, despite higher average temperatures.
248 Time-varying temperature associations were also observed but only for subjective heat strain
249 and negative mood, suggesting partial seasonal adaptation across the summer, particularly
250 within moderate temperature ranges (approximately 21–26 °C for heat strain and 19–23 °C
251 for negative mood). No seasonal adaptation patterns were observed for stress, fatigue, or
252 cognitive state.

253 4.1. Temperature and subjective heat strain

254 As expected, subjective heat strain showed the strongest association with temperature,
255 compared to mental health outcomes, and was also associated with relative humidity and step
256 counts, reflecting the close relationship between thermal exposure and perceived heat burden.
257 This contrasts with mood, fatigue, and cognitive state, which are influenced by a broader
258 range of factors and less directly associated with heat. Our findings align with previous work
259 showing subjective thermal strain indices are highly sensitive to workers' heat exposure^{37,38}.

260 Lower subjective heat strain later in the summer is consistent with evidence of intra-seasonal
261 adaptation in subjective heat perception. Previous studies have reported improved thermal
262 comfort at comparable temperatures later in the warm season (but not at the within-
263 participant level)²¹ and increased use of behavioural cooling strategies following sustained
264 heat exposure³⁹. Together, these findings suggest that subjective heat responses may evolve
265 across a summer through combined physiological and behavioural pathways. However, our
266 results also suggest potential limits to adaptation, as improvements were mainly observed up
267 to approximately 26°C; after this threshold physiological and behavioural adaptations may
268 be insufficient to alleviate the perceived strain experienced by outdoor workers.

269 4.2. Temperature and mood-related outcomes

270 Higher temperatures were associated with worse mood-related outcomes (anger, negative
271 mood, and stress). Evidence from experimental studies is mixed, likely reflecting differences
272 in heat intensity and exposure duration^{40,41}. Observational studies suggest that mood
273 responses to temperature depend on thermal exposure, duration, and individual discomfort
274 levels, which is consistent with our findings^{21,42,43}. We observed small but significant
275 improvements in anger and negative mood later in the summer, along with time-varying
276 temperature effects for negative mood. No seasonal or time-varying effects were observed
277 for stress. These findings suggest that seasonal mood adaptation may occur primarily within
278 moderate temperature ranges and may diminish beyond higher heat thresholds. However,
279 because no previous studies have longitudinally assessed within-individual changes in self-
280 reported mood in heat-exposed populations, direct comparison with existing literature
281 remains limited.

282 4.3. Temperature, fatigue, and cognitive state

283 Associations between temperature and fatigue and cognitive state were somewhat stronger
284 than those observed for mood-related outcomes, but not as pronounced as for subjective heat
285 strain, and showed no seasonal changes or time-varying temperature effects. Previous studies
286 indicate that fatigue⁴⁴ and cognition^{45,46} can be affected by heat exposure, particularly when
287 exposure is prolonged or sufficient to increase core or skin temperature. Some studies showed
288 controlled acclimation of adults over short timeframes (repeated heat exposure from 4 to 15

289 days) resulted in reductions in subjective fatigue⁴⁷⁻⁵⁰ and attenuated heat-related cognitive
290 impairments⁵¹. Our participants' in situ heat exposure (extending well beyond 4–15-day
291 periods) make the absence of longitudinal changes in fatigue and cognitive responses difficult
292 to directly compare with findings from controlled, short-term acclimation studies.
293 Accordingly, further longitudinal research specifically designed to examine intra-seasonal
294 adaptation processes in occupational settings is warranted.

295 4.4. Strengths and limitations

296 This study provides novel evidence on intra-seasonal psychological adaptation to heat using
297 intensive longitudinal data and time-varying analyses. Strengths include: (i) the continuous
298 three-month monitoring, enabling a detailed characterization of how vulnerability to heat
299 evolves within the season⁵³; (ii) the focus on psychological outcomes beyond physiological
300 indicators, and (iii) the focus on outdoor workers, a population that is both understudied and
301 disproportionately exposed to heat-related risks. Limitations include our small,
302 predominantly male and highly educated sample, who showed relatively good baseline
303 mental health, limiting generalizability to the wider workforce, other climatic regions, and
304 individuals with poorer mental health. Our data was collected over a single summer,
305 preventing distinction between short-term seasonal adjustments and longer-term adaptation
306 across several summers. Behavioural cooling strategies were not measured despite being a
307 potential mediator of the association between heat and psychological outcomes. Despite these
308 limitations, our study offers valuable insights into how psychological responses to heat can
309 change within a season, providing a foundation for future research, and interventions to
310 support worker resilience in high-risk settings.

311 5. Conclusion

312 Psychological adaptation to heat appears to occur within a single summer among outdoor
313 workers, particularly for subjective heat strain and some mood outcomes. Importantly, these
314 adaptations were most evident at moderate temperatures, suggesting limits to within-season
315 acclimatization under more extreme heat. These findings underscore the potential for partial
316 psychological adaptation, while also highlighting the ongoing vulnerability of workers
317 during hotter periods. Overall, our results provide a foundation for future studies to explore

318 mechanisms of adaptation and inform strategies for protecting outdoor workers throughout
319 the warm season.

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